

D1.1 Comprehensive overview of the project

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Executive summary

This deliverable addresses the complex landscape surrounding the introduction of steel additive manufactured components in industrial and aerospace applications. It navigates through studies, research findings and potential impacts, highlighting the evolving dynamics of predictive models on surface finishing operations and the challenges associated with the final surface integrity of functional components.

Additive Manufacturing (AM) is widely used in the manufacture and repair of metallic parts. The process provides a means for components of intricate geometry to be manufactured using a laser beam with material being delivered into the laser path on the desired substrate. Parts produced by AM commonly present poor surface quality and wide dimensional accuracy; thus, machining processes are required to obtain optimal surface integrity. Surface properties have an enormous influence on features such as dimensional accuracy, friction coefficient and wear, thermal and electric resistance, fatigue limit, corrosion, appearance and cost. Hence, optimum surface integrity is crucial for the proper functionality of machined workpieces.

SuPreAM project aims at optimizing surface integrity of AMed + machined steel components to reduce manufacturing expenditures at the steel industrial sector through the minimization of scrap and avoidance of re-processing loops. Predictive models of finishing operations will be developed considering the influence of AM technology and steel grades, machining operations, strategies and process parameters on machinability and surface properties of AMed components, enabling the identification of main variables affecting surface integrity. Particle Finite Element Method will be developed for the first time to study of AMed machined steels and AM parameters will be adjusted for a new quality of lean maraging steel.

Two representative case studies have been selected. In both cases, components are real in-use parts proposed for improvement with requirements very closely related to surface quality: 1) a plastic injection mould, surface finish is crucial to ensure quality of moulded parts and mould behaviour (thermal fatigue and wear resistance); 2) a structural component for aerospace application, which requires fatigue resistance. Demonstrators of both case-studies will be produced and used for model validation and comparison with conventional steels.

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Terminology and Acronyms

AM	Additive Manufacturing
3D	Three Dimension
AMed	Additive Manufactured
ANN	Artificial Neural Network
ASTM	American Society for Testing and Materials
BJ	Binder Jetting
BTF	Buy-To-Fly
CEN CENELEC	European Committee for Standardization / European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization
CNC	Computerized Numerical Control
CRMs	Critical Raw Materials
CVD	Chemical Vapor Depositions
DED	Directed Energy Deposition
DED-GMA	Direct Energy Deposition – Gas Metal Arc
DED-L	Direct Energy Deposition – Laser
DEI	Digitizing European Industry
DoA	Document Of Activities
DRX	Dynamic Recrystallization
E	Young's Modulus
EC	European Commission
EDM	Electric Discharge Machining
EU	European Union
FEM	Finite Element Method
FE-SEM	Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope
FTE	Full-Time Employees
GD	Green Deal
HR-EBSD	High-Resolution Electron Backscattered Diffraction
HSM	High-Speed Machining
HT	Heat Treatment
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
LB-PBF	Laser-Based Powder Bed Fusion
ME	Material Extrusion
ML	Machine Learning
MRR	Material Removal Rate
MSP	Multi-Stakeholder Platform
PBF	Powder Bed Fusion
PFEM	Particle Finite Element Method

PH	Precipitation Hardening
PVD	Physical Vapor Deposition
Ra	Arithmetical Mean Deviation of The Assessed Profile
Rq	Root Mean Square Deviation of The Assessed Profile
Rz	Maximum Height of Profile
Sa	Arithmetical Mean Height of The Scale Limited Surface
Sal	Auto-Correlation Length
Sdr	Developed Interfacial Area Ratio
Sq	Root Mean Square Height of The Scale-Limited Surface
Str	Texture –Aspect Ratio
Sz	Maximum Height of The Scale-Limited Surface
TCs	Technical Committees
WAAM	Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing
WEDM	Wire Electric Discharge Machining
WP	Work Package
XRD	X-Ray Diffraction
ZDM	Zero Defect Manufacturing

1. Introduction

Additive Manufacturing (AM) is amongst the most disruptive technologies and increasingly being used in the manufacture and repair of metallic parts. In the steel sector this technology opens the possibility to develop innovative alloys with similar (or better) outstanding material properties as the already available high-performance alloys, but as a cost-effective alternative, and the process provides a means for components of intricate geometry and desirable properties to be manufactured. Nevertheless, a major deficit of the AM processes is the limited resulting surface quality and dimensional accuracy. Functional surfaces need to be machined to be within the desired tolerances. Additionally, support structures on overhanging surfaces have to be mechanically removed from the part. Inhomogeneities in the deposition process as a result of non-uniform cooling and porosity are shown to have a deleterious effect on the surface integrity of the resulting part and the machinability of such components. Subtractive machining processes with a defined cutting edge are used in particular for post-processing. This is currently done based on experiences gathered from decades of conventional, subtractive manufacturing methods.

SuPreAM project aims at optimizing surface integrity of AMed + machined steel components to reduce manufacturing expenditures at the steel industrial sector through the minimization of scrap and avoidance of re-processing loops. Predictive models of finishing operations will be developed considering the influence of AM technology and steel grades, machining operations, strategies and process parameters on machinability and surface properties of AMed components, enabling the identification of main variables affecting surface integrity.

The objective of this deliverable D1.1 is to provide a comprehensive overview of SuPreAM project, including an updated State of the Art, the description of the problem, the proposed approach and the main outcomes of the project.

2. State of the Art

2.1 Metal additive manufacturing processes

In recent years, additive manufacturing processes for metals have revolutionized the landscape of modern manufacturing. This innovative approach, also known as 3D metal printing, has emerged as a transformative technology that empowers engineers and manufacturers to fabricate complex and intricate metal components with unprecedented precision and efficiency. Additive manufacturing involves building up layers of metal powder or wire, layer by layer, to create intricate structures. This paradigm shift in production techniques not only offers remarkable design freedom but also presents new possibilities for optimizing material usage, reducing waste, and accelerating product development cycles. This technology holds the potential to redefine traditional supply chains and open doors to a new era of advanced, customized, and sustainable metal fabrication. Metal AM processes are categorized according to ASTM/ISO 52900:2017 into four broad categories: material extrusion (ME), binder jetting (BJ), powder bed fusion (PBF), and directed energy deposition (DED).

Table 1. Lists of the four metal additive manufacturing categories defined by ASTM/ISO 52900:2017 (Armstrong, 2022).

Process	Abbreviation	Mode	Typical Applications
Material extrusion	ME	Material is selectively dispensed through a nozzle or orifice	Functional metal parts, prototyping
Binder jetting	BJ	A liquid bonding agent is selectively deposited to join powder materials	Functional metal parts, low-rate production runs of non-critical components
Directed energy deposition	DED	Focused thermal energy is used to fuse materials by melting as they are being deposited	Functional metal parts, repairs, adding material to existing parts
Powder bed fusion	PBF	Thermal energy selectively fuses regions of a powder bed	Functional metal parts, functional prototyping

Amongst the different AM technologies, the most typical approaches for 3D printing of metals for real use-case applications are going to be studied in SuPreAM: Laser-Based Powder Bed Fusion (LB-PBF) and Direct Energy Deposition (DED) (Cao, 2023) (DebRoy, 2018), (Herzog, 2016). LB-PBF is one of the most widespread AM technologies for functional components in several sectors of application (industrial, medical, aerospace, amongst others). Raw material is used in fine powder format, staying in a flat “bed” which is selectively consolidated under the effect of a high-power laser source (see Figure 1. Scheme of Laser-Based Powder Bed Fusion (LB-PBF).Figure 1). Though being a highly reliable process, critical points, like porosity found in the final components and thermal effects due to laser action, can ultimately lead to warping and other defects.

DED encompasses a series of technologies in which focused thermal energy is applied at the same time as the raw material. The basic working principle is the same in all of them: the movable dispensing systems feed raw material in the precise spot where the energy source is working, consolidating into the part and subsequently building the whole geometry (see Figure 2). Raw material format (powder, solid wire) and energy source (laser, gas arc, electric arc) varies from one system to another, resulting in several variants of the process (“laser cladding” or “DED-L; Direct Energy Deposition – Laser”, “WAAM- wire arc additive manufacturing”, “DED-GMA; Direct Energy Deposition – Gas Metal Arc”). DED technologies are known to feature poor surface quality and aesthetics, usually requiring post processing. On the other hand, it is a versatile and flexible AM approach, which allows growing new geometries into pre-existing components, especially useful for repairing operations. In the frame of SuPreAM the design concept of hybrid AM approach for structural components manufacturing will be developed and identified as hybrid (Conventional machining + DED).

Figure 1. Scheme of Laser-Based Powder Bed Fusion (LB-PBF).

Figure 2. Scheme of Direct Energy Deposition (DED).

2.2 Post processing strategies for Additive Manufactured steels

The surface of AM products is influenced by the pores, cavities and partially melted powder which leads to poor surface quality. The surface integrity of the printed components such as surface roughness, microstructure, corrosion and wear resistance, surface topography and microhardness can be modified using post processing processes together with the AM technology. The selection of surface modification technique or process is based on the output parameters that need to be modified. Moreover, the surface modifications can overcome the issues due to partially melted powders and undesired layer thickness (Vijaya-Kumar & Velmurugan, 2022). Existing literature reveals that a wide range of post-processing techniques have been used on as-built 3D-printed metal parts for different purposes such as surface treatments, homogenization of the microstructure, relaxation of residual stresses, closure of pores, and improvement of properties (Reza-Khosravani, 2023). Post-processing machining of AMed components is required to achieve end-user final requirements (Figure 3). Thus, the materials will be subjected to mechanical, thermal, topological as well as metallurgical alterations. Mechanical modifications include change in hardness, plastic deformations and induced residual stresses that could dramatically deteriorate functionality of the end-use parts. Heat-affected layer is due to thermal variation taking place during machining whereas topological alteration mainly covers variation in the surface morphology. Metallurgical alteration consists of phase transformation, recrystallization on the surface and sub-surface which in turn effect microstructural change (Thakur, 2016). These diversified types of alterations directly influence the quality of the surface or near surface region of the machined component (Tabatabaeian, 2021). Therefore, is key to obtain a proper surface integrity as well as metallurgical and mechanical characteristics of surface and sub-surface for enhancing mechanical behaviour, dimensional accuracy and durability of the machined components made of AM.

Figure 3. An example of a typical metal AM process workflow.

Strategies will be defined according to three different topics: 1) machining processes; 2) finishing processes and 3) heat treatment. These strategies will consider:

1) Machining processes:

- Cutting machining parameters: cutting speed, feed rate, depth of cut, cut orientation and lubricant/cooling system.
 - Cutting tool materials and coatings (chemical composition and properties), tool geometry and tool hardness.
 - Electrical discharge machining parameters: peak current intensity, discharge duration, effective discharge frequency.
- 2) Finishing processes:
- Grinding, polishing, sandblasting and other finishing techniques (e.g., burnishing).
 - Thermochemical treatments (e.g., nitriding).
 - Hard coating application: Physical Vapor Deposition (PVD) and Chemical Vapor Deposition (CVD).
- 3) Heat treatment:
- Stress relieving, Annealing, Quenching, Tempering and other treatments.

2.2.1 Machining processes

Conventional machining processes, such as milling, drilling and turning, are the traditional manufacturing processes employed to enhance the manufactured parts dimensional accuracy and surface quality. Owing to the popularity and acceptability at a wide level, they are also employed in AM for the post-processing of manufactured parts. Bai et al. studied the machining of the ASTM A131 steel AM components. They used computerized numerical control (CNC) milling machine. After post-processing, the samples' surface roughness was smoothed from 22.7 to 0.6 μm . It was found that the surface roughness upgraded with an increase in the cutting speed and a reduction in tool feeding rate (Bai, 2020). Barragan et al. studied the machining of 316L SS part obtained by hybrid manufacturing, direct energy deposition (DED) and high-speed machining (HSM). They used CNC high speed milling machine. After post-processing, the samples' surface roughness (S_a) was smoothed on the top area from 60.0 to 1.0 μm and in the lateral area from 42.7 to 4.2 μm . The reduction was above 90%, indicating milling is an essential step for reducing the roughness values of additive manufacturing technologies. It was found that for complex surface geometry a decrease in the tool feeding rate may be applied (Barragan, 2023). Conventional machining processes have proved their viability for the post-processing of AM parts. They are commonly applied to amplify surface characteristics such as surface roughness and skewness. However, their effect on hardness improvement has not been proved yet. These findings are valid in the case of the milling and turning process (Mahmood, 2022). Cutting tool materials and coatings have a huge impact on the surface integrity of machined components. Ongoing tool development is aimed at creating tools that can cope with multiple issues presented by steel alloys. Manufacturers seek tools that are sharper yet stronger, with coatings and geometries designed to overcome heat, pressure, chemical and adhesion mechanisms of wear (Li e. a., 2023), (Muhammad Umar Farooq, 2023), (Danish, 2023) (Gong, 2019), (Oyelola, 2016), (Thakur, 2016). Cutting tool damaging mechanisms directly impact on component surface properties (Ramírez, 2022). Cutting tool wear can be classified into several types: (i) adhesive wear associated with shear plane deformation, (ii) abrasive wear

resulting from hard particle cutting action, (iii) diffusion wear occurring at high temperatures, and (iv) fracture wear such as chipping due to fatigue.

Tool wear processes generally occur in combination with predominant wear mode, dependent upon cutting conditions, workpiece and tooling materials, and tool insert geometry (Agapiou, 2013). Lubricant/cooling fluid has also a strong effect. Consortium members will explore the use of most suitable lubricants for this application, based on knowledge gained in LUBRINTEL project (LUBRINTEL, 2019), where lubricants for machining of AMed titanium are designed and developed. Main features of cutting tools wear are shown in Figure 4, additionally features can be measured (such as build up edge in case it is formed).

Figure 4. Features of machining tool wear measurements.

Chip morphology and composition is also an indicative of machinability and tool and workpiece materials behaviour. As an example, “C” and “9” shape chips or short spiral chips ($l < 50$ mm) are acceptable, but chips irregularly entangled (wrapping around the tool) or connected in form of irregular waves (which indicates scatter) may harm the finished surface (Seco Tools, 2023).

1 RIBBON CHIPS*	2 TUBULAR CHIPS*	3 SPIRAL CHIPS	4 WASHER-TYPE HELICAL CHIPS*	5 CONICAL HELICAL CHIPS*	6 ARC CHIPS**	7 ELEMENTAL CHIPS	8 NEEDLE CHIPS
1.1 Long	2.1 Long	3.1 Flat	4.1 Long	5.1 Long	6.1 Connected		
1.2 Short	2.2 Short	3.2 Conical	4.2 Short	5.2 Short	6.2 Loose		
1.3 Snarled	2.3 Snarled		4.3 Snarled	5.3 Snarled			

Figure 5. The ISO 3685-1977 (E) containing the standard chip forms (Viharos, 2003).

Wire electric discharge machining (EDM) is a non-traditional machining method that is used to cut hard, conductive materials. Wire EDM is a high-precision process that can meet very

tight tolerances and is employed in several industries including the aerospace and automotive industries. While wire EDM is increasingly being used in the AM industry, very little research has been conducted on the wire EDM of additively manufactured parts. Recently, wire EDM has been used in the additive manufacturing (AM) industry for metal part post-processing and removal from build plates. The effect of wire EDM (WEDM) cutting voltage, pulse-on time and pulse-off time on the machining time, resultant surface roughness, and hardness of both AM and wrought 316L stainless steel samples was measured by Bicknell (Bicknell, 2018). The EDM machining time for the AM 316L sample was significantly lower than the machining time for the wrought 316L sample. This might be due to the different microstructures present in the samples. The surface roughness and hardness were slightly higher for the wrought 316L sample. The parameter that most affected the machining time for both samples was the EDM cutting voltage. As the EDM cutting voltage increased, the machining time decreased. In another study Boban (Boban, 2022) studied wire feed rate, wire tension, and dielectric flushing pressure effect on the machining, resultant surface roughness, and micro hardness of AM AISi10Mg and Ti6Al4V alloys. Results shown that roughness improvement was above 79% in both samples regard to as-built parameters. Better surface finishes were reach at lower pulse on time parameters. Apparently, the prolonged spark discharges produced at elevated pulse on time settings, can produce relatively big and deeper craters for one sample and formation of microcracks for the other. Microcracks formation can be resolved by performing WEDM at higher servo voltages as well, where the machining gap maintained between the wire electrode and the workpiece also increases. Consequently, the net thermal energy transferred to the workpiece will be lesser relative to the energy transfer at lower servo voltage. This means that the magnitude of thermal stresses will be minimized, therefore, the microcracks formation is hindered. Micro-Vickers hardness test was performed, and it was discovered that thermal effects can affect the hardness value more for the AISi10Mg sample than for Ti6Al4V. The reason can be attributed to the high thermal conductivity of aluminium which aids the efficient transfer of heat energy deeper in the workpiece. Consequently, the heat affected zone will be significant in AISi10Mg. The interaction between wire EDM and AMed alloys is not yet fully understood. Further research is needed to analyse the fully interaction of wire EDM parameters on AM alloys and the effects of microstructure on EDM machining time.

2.2.2 Finishing processes

Abrasive finishing, including grinding and polishing, has the capability to finish conventional as well as AMed parts. Compared with machining such as milling and other alternative finishing processes, grinding has advantages for producing tight tolerances, fine finish and desired compressive residual stress in the ground surface layer. The advantages can become more substantial for difficult-to-machine materials commonly used in 3D printing, because the self-sharpening property of abrasive grains extends abrasive tool life longer than that of other cutting tools. Grinding wheels can be prepared with complex forms for finishing 3D-printed parts. Using a grinding process with a pre-formed wheel is an effective way to finish a relatively large batch of parts. In addition to precision grinding, abrasive tools can be also used for free-form finishing in manual or robotic mode (Modern Machine Shop, 2023).

Nitriding of ferritic/martensitic steels relies on the ingress of nitrogen into the solid and brings about the formation of an iron-based nitride scale at the surface (the non-uniform compound layer), and the formation of alloying-element nitrides dispersed in the bcc matrix (the diffusion

zone). Nitriding of maraging steels is known to improve fatigue, wear and corrosion performance. Gaseous nitriding, as compared to plasma-nitriding, is particularly beneficial for AM components with a complex geometry and rough surface finish. Nitriding of AMed M300 is a feasible and highly promising post-processing treatment to obtain deep hardened case and high surface hardness. Gaseous nitriding is especially suitable for complex geometries and provides uniform case depths (Funch, 2022). Hard coating (e.g. Physical Vapor Deposition -PVD-, Chemical Vapor Depositions -CVD-) application on a 3D-printed mould might prove to reduce the impact of wear, friction, harsh chemicals and materials or heat, increasing mould life and performance (Additivemanufacturing, 2023). This line of thinking is now extending to 3D-printed production parts, too.

During last year several articles and reviews on machining and finishing processes for additive manufactured parts have been published: maraging steel (Tamura, 2022), Ti alloy (Vargheses, 2021), Ni alloy (Careri, 2021), and various materials (Hashmi, 2021), (Pérez, 2021), (Velu, 2021), (Shiyas, 2021). Finishing operations of parts produced by additive manufacturing are nowadays an important challenge and a hot topic in this field to boost AM industrial implementation.

2.2.3 Heat treatments

It is well known that most of the materials manufactured with AM technologies need heat treatment (HT) after printing so that the desired microstructure and, as consequence, the goal properties are achieved. Therefore, the need for a specific HT design for new materials is evident. For commercial materials it is also known that LB-PBF machine provider companies include specification sheets where a recommended standard HT is indicated. However, experience and several investigations (Cheruvathur, 2016), (Nezhadfar, 2018), (Yeon, 2022) have proven that optimization of the HT is mandatory when the requirements are high. For instance, in the case of one of the most extendedly used materials in LB-PBF, the precipitation hardening martensitic stainless steel 17-4PH, is very prone to the capture of nitrogen during high temperature processes (in the case of AM this can take place during atomization, manufacturing and HT of the component). In some cases, the result of a non-optimized HT can lead to the formation of δ -ferrite, excessive amount of retained austenite that can cause a reduction on the final properties or even hot cracking of the component despite the standard HT recommended by machine manufacturers has been followed. This is due to the high complexity of the process and the several variables included from quality/provider of the raw material, machine model, process parameters, etc., and puts into perspective the need of the design and optimization of a specific HT even for commercial materials.

Additionally, it is worth noting that heat treatments allow for the tailored selection of properties for a given application. Often, it involves a balance between different properties, such as increasing hardness and strength at the expense of reducing toughness or elongation. The reverse option is equally possible. Depending on the material, it may not be as straightforward, but what is certain is that it enables the customization of the final component properties to align with the most critical requirements of its application.

The study of heat treatments combines simulation techniques, sample-scale tests on dilatometry equipment, metallographic characterizations, and scaling up to larger

components. Controlling all stages of the development of a heat treatment is essential to ensure the satisfactory final performance of the component.

2.3 Surface integrity

Surface integrity obtained in machined parts is the result of a material removal process due to relative motion between tool and part, however the surface topography/functionality generation mechanisms are not fully understood, there is a complex interaction and cause effect relationships between a number of factors that influence surface integrity (Figure 6). In general terms, surface integrity can be divided into two aspects: first the external topography of surfaces (surface finish) and second, the microstructure, mechanical properties and residual stresses of the subsurface layer. In this manner, surface integrity is commonly defined as “the topographical, mechanical, chemical and metallurgical state of a machined surface and its relationship to functional performance”. An understanding of surface integrity is a powerful tool to avoid failures, enhance component integrity and reduce overall costs (Lee, 2021), (Paulo, 2010). Surface properties have an enormous influence on features such as dimensional accuracy, friction coefficient and wear, thermal and electric resistance, fatigue limit, corrosion, post-processing requirements, appearance and cost. Optimal surface integrity is crucial for the proper functionality of machined workpieces.

Figure 6. Parameters affecting surface integrity (adapted from Benardos (Benardos, 2003), according to SuPreAM consortium knowledge).

2.3.1 Surface integrity characterization

In general terms, surface integrity is commonly defined as “the topographical, mechanical, chemical and metallurgical state of a machined surface and its relationship to functional performance”. The different topics and categories to describe surface integrity are summarized in the following table.

Table 2. Surface integrity characterization undertaken in SuPreAM project.

Topics	Categories	Examples of surface integrity anomalies
Surface topography	Surface Macro anomalies	Roughness irregularities, scores, cracks, inclusions, orange peel, chatter, burr
	Surface Micro anomalies	Flaking, smearing, laps, plucking.
Microstructure and metallurgical changes	Thermal affected zone	Recast layer, redissolution of phases.
	Mechanical affected zone	Distorted layer, grain deformation
	Heat and mechanical affected zone	White layer, recrystallized zone
Mechanical properties changes	Material hardness changes	Deviation of hardness in surface or in depth
	Residual stresses	Deviation of residual stresses in surface or in depth
	Mechanical and tribological behaviour	Low fatigue strength due to surface defects, changes in tribological behaviour

2.3.1.1 Surface roughness

Machined surfaces will be characterized in terms of surface roughness parameters to describe the topography, waviness and finishing lay. In doing so, surface roughness parameters will be calculated from topographic images with an image analysis software. 2D amplitude parameters, such as Ra, Rq and Rz, and the corresponding parameters in 3D (Sa, Sq and Sz) can be obtained. In some cases, amplitude parameters are not able to distinguish between surfaces with high quantity of peaks, valleys and surfaces with less quantity of higher peaks and deeper valleys, although these surfaces have the same Ra, Sa values. Thus, spatial and hybrid parameters will be analysed to supply more complete surface information (see Table 3).

Table 3. Main surface roughness parameters studied in SuPreAM project.

2D and 3D amplitude parameters		
Parameter	Definition	Calculation and use
Ra, Sa	<i>Roughness average</i> is the main height as calculated over the entire measured length (L) or area (a)	$Ra = \frac{1}{L} \int_0^L z dx$; $Sa = \iint_a Z(x,y) dx dy$ Typically used to describe machined surfaces. Useful for detecting general variations in overall profile height and for monitoring manufacturing processes.
Rq, Sq	The <i>Root means square (rms) average</i> between the height deviations and the mean line/ surface.	$Rq = \sqrt{\frac{1}{L} \int_0^L z^2 dx}$; $Sq = \sqrt{\iint_a (Z(x,y))^2 dx dy}$ Describes the finish of optical surfaces. It represents the standard deviation of the profile heights and is used in computations of skew and kurtosis.
Rz, Sz	The <i>Average maximum profile</i> of the ten greatest peak-to-valley separations in the evaluation area.	$Rz = \frac{1}{10} \left[\sum_{j=1}^{10} H_j - \sum_{j=1}^{10} L_j \right]$ Rz is useful for evaluating surface texture on samples where the presence of high peaks or deep valleys is of functional significance.
3D spectral parameters		
Parameter	Definition	Use
Str	Texture –aspect ratio	Indicates isotropy level. It has a value between 0 and 1. Values near 1 correspond to isotropic surfaces (the same characteristics in all directions), values near 0 correspond to anisotropic surfaces (with oriented and/or periodical structure).
Sal	Auto-correlation length	Expresses the content in wavelength of the surface. A high value indicates that the surface has mainly high wavelengths (low frequencies).
3D hybrid parameters		
Parameter	Definition	Use
Sdr	Developed interfacial area ratio	Indicates the complexity of the surface comparing the curvilinear surface with the support surface. A completely flat surface will have a Sdr near 0%. A complex surface will have a Sdr of some percent.

2.3.1.2 Microstructure and metallurgical changes

Other surface integrity aspects to be considered in SuPreAM project are the microstructure and metallurgical changes of surface and sub-surface layer of machined samples. During machining of AM steel alloys, surface is subjected to high mechanical (high stress and strain) and thermal load (high temperature and quenching) which may cause some microstructural

and metallurgical alterations. These alterations include recrystallized, highly deformed grains and different layers with varying intensity of deformation in the surface and sub-surface of the component. In depth analysis of various characteristics of these surface and sub-surface alterations will be carried out with the aid of advanced techniques. Cross sections of machined samples will be obtained and analysed by means of optical microscopy, Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope (FE-SEM) and High-Resolution Electron Backscattered Diffraction (HR-EBSD) to get further insight in the microstructure and crystallography. HR-EBSD is an advanced characterization technique which is particularly helpful in the study of machining-induced deformation providing quantitative information about the grain orientation along with intragranular misorientation. In that sense, processing of HR-EBSD maps will have as a result the microstructure characterization of the mechanical and thermal affected zones (Park, 2021), (Haghdadi, 2021).

2.3.1.3 Mechanical properties changes: hardness and residual stresses

Changes in mechanical properties of steel alloys, typically in the form of hardness and residual stress due to machining induced deformation is a common occurrence after post-processing. Such mechanical changes can be effectively captured by progressively measuring hardness, elastic modulus, residual stresses and micro-tensile tests. Nanoindentation experiments will be performed in order to study more in detail the different layers formed in the first micrometres below the machined surface in terms of hardness and Young's Modulus (E). These damage mechanisms can be correlated with micromechanical changes, such as local variations of E when surface and sub-surface plastic deformation or micro cracks are present (see Figure 7a). However, the influence of the surface integrity in the properties of AMed steels is still a pending task. Large scale tensile testing is a commonly used test to quantify the elastic modulus, yield-, ultimate-, and fracture-strength of materials. However, while these tests provide valuable insights into the overall material properties, they average out the effects of the direct influence of local subsurface deformation due to machining and finishing process. In this regard, micro-tensile testing is required to evaluate the influence of machining induced deformation.

Figure 7. Decrease in value of Young's modulus (E) in a tool steel sample when applied stress (σ) is increased monotonically.

Within the framework of surface integrity investigations, special emphasis is given to the measurement of residual stresses because they contribute directly to premature failure of components. Residual stresses are also a sensitive indicator for variations of machining parameters and tool properties and so can be a powerful evaluation criterion for machining processes as well. Residual stresses could be categorized by different length scale: type I (residual stresses on macrolevel), type II (microscale stresses nearly always exist due to anisotropic material properties on grain scale) and type III (nanoscale stresses due to coherency and dislocation) (Li C. e., 2018). Type II and type III residual stresses have very limited effect on the material's mechanical properties, but type I stress since its macroscale characteristics would affect the surface integrity. In this phase measurement of residual stresses of type I will be conducted by means of X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) and Hole-Drilling strain-gage method. XDR technique is based on carrying out localized attack by electro-polishing a in a surface region, then residual stresses are measured as the material is being removed. As a result, a residual stress profile is obtained as a function of depth, which provides more information than a single surface measurement. The maximum depth that can be achieved with this method is around 0.5 mm. Hole-drilling strain-gage method is based on drilling a small hole on the surface to be analysed. To do this, a rosette with 3 strain gauges must be installed in the test area, then a hole is drilled at the point of intersection of the axes of the 3 gauges and the strains are measured as material is removed by machining a hole. Then the residual stresses are quantified using the empirical expressions developed in ASTM E837-13 (ASTM, 2013). The drilled holes have a diameter of 1.8-2.0 mm and 1 mm depth. Machining of the hole can be carried out in 0.05 mm steps allowing the measurement of residual stress evolution as material is removed. Results of different techniques will be compared in order to study their resolution and convenience in order to study residual stressed in machined AM parts.

2.3.2 Surface integrity prediction in machining/cutting/finishing processes

Previous research projects focused on the adaptation of robots, sensors and actuators to improve positioning accuracy for online manufacturing control related to the part quality. Main issues promoted in European projects' calls for manufacturing, such as NMBP, FoF and Horizon Europe Cluster 4 calls outline concepts of advanced monitoring and maintenance as well as the system automation and integration i.e. (SERENA, 2017) and (INTEGRADDE, 2018) projects. However, the influence of workpiece, specifically of AMed materials, and cutting tool materials has not been fully addressed and significant challenges for the industries and manufacturers still remain. On the other hand, (FATECO, 2018) and IMMAC (Villalibre, 2019) projects indeed evaluated machinability of different steel grades (none of them produced by additive manufacturing) considering microstructural effects and chemical composition of workpiece materials, though other factors such as process and machine tool modelling have not been taken into account. (PALMS, 2017) project addresses a plasma additive layer manufacture smoothing technology to improve mechanical resistance of AMed parts, however predictive models are not considered. Finally, in a recent publication an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) to predict the surface roughness of additively manufactured Ti6Al4V alloy specimens after being blasted and electropolished is developed (Soler, 2022), no machining/cutting processes have been taken into account.

2.4 Modelling of machining/cutting/finishing processes

2.4.1 Cutting machining process modelling

Metal cutting or machining is a process in which a thin layer of metal, the chip, is removed by a wedge-shaped tool from a large body. Cutting is a complex physical phenomenon in which several phenomena are present: i.e., friction, adiabatic shear bands, excessive heating, large and high-rate strains. Tool geometry, rake angle and cutting speed play a significant role in chip morphology, cutting forces, energy consumption and tool wear. Due to the complex physical process of cutting, machining processes are one of the most challenging industrial problems to be analysed from the numerical simulation point of view (Wedberg, 2012), (Svoboda, 2010).

There is a wide range of chip flows that can be freely formed, depending on the material and cutting conditions. The formation of all types of chips involves the shearing of the work material in the region of a plane extending from the tool edge to the position where the upper surface of the chip leaves the work surface. In this region, a very large amount of deformation takes place in a noticeably short time interval, and not all metals and alloys can withstand this strain without fracture. The vast majority of formed chips can be classified as follows: discontinuous, continuous, continuous with build-up-edge and serrated chip. Chip formation and morphology are directly related to part roughness and surface integrity.

Figure 8. Temperature distribution (in K) during chip formation varying cutting speed on 2D turning of Ti6Al4V (Rodríguez J. , 2013).

Simulation of machining processes where the workpiece material is highly deformed during metal cutting is a major challenge of the finite element method (FEM). The main problem that must be faced when using a conventional FEM model is the large mesh distortions that appears in the attack zone of the cutting bladed. Traditional Lagrangian approaches such as FEM cannot properly resolve large deformations. High element distortion has always been a matter of concern, limiting the analysis to incipient chip formation in some studies (Oñate, 2014), (Ali, 2013), (Bajic, 2012). Besides, FEM with a Eulerian formulation requires prior knowledge of the chip geometry, which, undoubtedly, restricts the range of cutting conditions to be analysed. Furthermore, serrated and discontinuous chip formation cannot be simulated. SuPreAM will apply Particle Finite Element Method (PFEM) to simulate machining process, which counteracts the typical difficulties of the finite element method (FEM), such as e.g., circumventing the mesh distortion problem and diminishing the error due to information transfer between evolving meshes. A particle method is a method that represents the of a physical problem by a collection of material points named particles. Another feature of particle methods is that all the physical and mathematical properties are tied to the particle itself and not to the elements as in FEM. Particle methods are advantageous for dealing with

both discrete and continuous problems where there are is a potential for internal separations, such as fracture they also avoid all the difficulties existing in both standard mesh and standard meshless methods. This technique has been successfully applied in the modelling of 2D linear cutting tests, see Figure 8, and is the best candidate to be considered in modelling complex problems, such as cutting processes of AMed components (Carbonell, 2020), (Carbonell, 2021), (Rodríguez J. M., 2022), (Rodríguez J. M., 2020), (Rodríguez J. M., 2020).

The numerical modelling of the cutting process can be used to characterize surface integrity and residual stresses in a machined component:

Surface Integrity describes the effect of the process parameters on the machining surface characteristics namely “residual stress, roughness, and microstructure. According to the literature (Sadeghifar, 2018), it is evident that surface roughness cannot be accurately predicted through numerical analysis. However, residual stress and microstructural evolution can be numerically predicted and provide evidence about surface finishing properties.

Residual stresses significantly impact mechanical component life and performance. Numerical prediction of these stresses is crucial but sensitive to applied conditions. Existing literature highlights variations in tool-workpiece interactions, boundary conditions, and stress extraction methods. Some studies emphasize tool unloading to ensure no contact, while others mention stopping the tool and releasing boundary constraints. Thermal unloading for strain relaxation is also considered in certain analyses. Moreover, cutting parameters including cutting speed, rake angle and uncut chip thickness influence the residual stress.

Changes in microstructure resulting from machining operations profoundly impact the fatigue life and corrosion resistance of machined components. Recently, there has been a focus on numerical simulation in orthogonal turning that considers microstructural alterations during cutting using the physical-based plastic constitutive models. The physical-based constitutive models indicate the knowledge of the physical processes giving rise to the plastic deformation. Generally, these models are developed based on the microstructural aspects of the deformation such as texture, grain size, dislocation density etc. incorporating the theory of thermodynamics, dislocation mechanics and kinetics of slips and glides (Bakhshan, 2023). The mechanisms of the physical-based models of metals encompass mobile or immobile dislocation-dislocation interaction for hardening and dynamic recovery, dynamic recrystallization, grain boundary sliding for softening are described by a mathematical expression denoting the plastic flow stress. During dynamic recrystallization (DRX), new strain-free grains are formed. This process involves the nucleation, growth, and merging of new grains in the deformed material because of the formation of new dislocation cells and their rearrangement. If a numerical model is capable to include these phenomena it can help to accurately predict recrystallized grain size during cutting or the microhardness variation induced in the surface and subsurface of a machined workpiece.

2.4.2 Numerical simulation of EDM process

Electrical Discharge Machining (EDM) involves complex physical processes that lead to the removal of material from two electrodes (i.e., tool and the workpiece). During the electrical discharge, the material reaches the melting temperature and partially evaporates. The material removal is due to the high pressure during the electric discharge due to the thermal expansion in the dielectric media (plasma channel) placed between the tool and the work piece, see Figure 9 for EDM spark description (Ubaid, 2018).

Figure 9. EDM spark description.

The material removal rate (MRR) is one of the key process parameters to be accounted for. This rate is strictly related to the electric discharge, that is: (i) the peak current intensity, (ii) the discharge duration, (iii) the effective discharge frequency. The material properties (i.e., workpiece conductivity, specific heat or density) are temperature dependent conforming a multi-physic thermos-electric-mechanical problem to be analysed. Moreover, both solid-to-liquid and liquid to vapour phase changes must be accounted for. An enthalpy-based formulation is generally preferred to deal with the quasi-isothermal phase transformations. The definition of the heat source (electric sparks) is another parameter of interest to be studied. Point source uniformly distributed or more sophisticated Gaussian power source can be analysed to check the sensitivity of the problem to this definition. In a FE framework, the material removal can be treated by element “deactivation”. Therefore, once accomplished the given criteria of material removal according to the MRR, the elements are removed from the computational domain (Zhang, 2019), (Maradia, 2015), (Wang T. e., 2013), (Shanmugam, 2013), (Moreira, 2023), (Ming, 2022), (Singh, 2020). This strategy will be combined with adaptive mesh refinement techniques, which will allow to concentrate the computational power in the area of the domain where the material removal is taking place. This approach has already been applied to standard AM processes (Moreira 2023)

2.5 Standardization for Additive Manufacturing

Additive Manufacturing for metallic materials is a recent production process and, therefore, the regulations for obtaining components for application are still under development. According to a study carried out by the Joint Research Centre (Joint Research Centre, 2014) the importance of standards is associated with the fact that they provide requirements, specifications, guidelines or characteristics that can be used consistently to ensure that materials, products, processes and services are fit for purpose. In this way, regulatory activity contributes to removing technical barriers to trade, guiding the industry towards new markets and boosting economic growth. Still in this context, standards facilitate and promote the transfer of technology and contribute to ensuring the safety of products, influencing the daily lives of citizens.

In general, normative activity allows:

- a) Promote the quality of products, processes and services;
- b) Promote improvements in quality of life, safety, health and environmental protection,
- c) Promote improvements in terms of the economic use of materials, energy and human resources,
- d) Facilitate the production and exchange of goods and clear and unambiguous communication between all interested parties, in an appropriate manner, using legally binding documents as a reference;
- e) Promote international trade by removing barriers caused by the diversity of national practices and industrial efficiency.

When we focus on Additive Manufacturing (AM) technology and its use for industrial purposes, the importance of consistent application and repeatability is highlighted, in order to guarantee widespread development and/or superior quality.

Following the above, it is crucial to invest in the standardization and certification of each element of AM technology (materials, equipment and processes), since the absence of standards in terms of materials, processes and products makes production with high levels of quality difficult.

However, the technological evolution that has occurred in this sector, combined with the increasing adaptation/use of new materials, processes and techniques, has hampered the development of AM standards. In consequence, this difficulty is also associated with the absence of a single repository where the great diversity of information that is being produced on AM methodologies is concentrated, as well as the identification of the responsible authorities. Currently, the main standardization bodies active worldwide at the level of Additive Manufacturing, with related Technical Committees (TCs), are:

- ASTM - American Society for Testing and Materials (F42),
- ISO - International Organization for Standardization (TC261)
- CEN CENELEC - European Committee for Standardization / European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization (TC438).

These bodies work in coordination to achieve a common goal: adopting a set of AM standards that will be applied if used globally. More specifically, ASTM F42 has a cooperation agreement with ISO TC 261 in the common adoption of AM standards.

In turn, CEN TC438 assesses which existing AM standards at ISO level can be adopted.

With the exponential growth of AM as a production process, there was a need for ASTM (American Society for Testing and Materials) to create a committee, in 2009, to define the standards to be met, this committee was called F42. These standards will range from raw materials, process/equipment, ending with finished components (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Areas of Interest for ASTM F42/ISO TC 261

There are also several European National Standardization Bodies that cover this topic, such as AFNOR in France, with the UNM 920 Additive Manufacturing committee; VDI in Germany with GPL Committee on Production and Logistics; AENOR in Spain with the AEN/CTN 116 committee including AM; SIS in Sweden with committee SIS/TK 563; and BSI in the UK with the AMT/8 committee.

AM standards are presented according to the following hierarchical structure:

1. General Standards - specific general concepts and common requirements
2. Standards by Category - specific process requirements or material categories
3. Specialized Standards - specific requirements for a material, process or application

Recently, the following standards related to AM were published:

[EN ISO 17296-2:2016](#) - Additive manufacturing - General principles - Part 2: Overview of process categories and feedstock (ISO 17296-2:2015)

[EN ISO 17296-3:2016](#) - Additive manufacturing - General principles - Part 3: Main characteristics and corresponding test methods (ISO 17296-3:2014)

[EN ISO 17296-4:2016](#) - Additive manufacturing - General principles - Part 4: Overview of data processing (ISO 17296-4:2014)

[EN ISO/ASTM 52900:2017](#) - Additive manufacturing - General principles - Terminology (ISO/ASTM 52900:2015)

[EN ISO/ASTM 52901:2018](#) - Additive manufacturing - General principles - Requirements for purchased AM parts (ISO/ASTM 52901:2017)

[EN ISO/ASTM 52915:2017](#) - Specification for additive manufacturing file format (AMF) Version 1.2 (ISO/ASTM 52915:2016)

[EN ISO/ASTM 52921:2016](#) - Standard terminology for additive manufacturing - Coordinate systems and test methodologies (ISO/ASTM 52921:2013)

[EN ISO/ASTM 52901:2017](#) - Additive manufacturing - General principles - Requirements for purchased AM parts

[EN ISO/ASTM 52910:2018](#) - Additive manufacturing -- Design -- Requirements, guidelines and recommendations

[ISO/ASTM 52941:2020](#) - Additive manufacturing -- System performance and reliability -- Acceptance tests for laser metal powder-bed fusion machines for metallic materials for aerospace application

[ISO/ASTM TR 52906:2022](#) - Additive manufacturing -- Non-destructive testing -- Intentionally seeding flaws in metallic parts

[ISO/ASTM 52909:2022](#) - Additive manufacturing -- Finished part properties -- Orientation and location dependence of mechanical properties for metal powder bed fusion

Despite realizing that we are facing a dynamic process, there is still a lot to be done in this area.

On June 13, 2018, the Workshop on Standardization for Digitizing European Industry was held in Brussels. During the workshop, it was explained what the creation of the DEI Working Group consisted of – MSP Working Group on standardization in support of Digitizing European Industry. This WG is the result of a collaboration between the Multi-Stakeholder Platform on ICT Standardization (MSP) and the Digitizing European Industry initiative (DEI), which brings together national ministries and actions related to the digitalization of industry, European standardization organizations, public-private partnerships and associations relevant European policies.

This Working Group's main objectives were:

1. Identify, as a starting point, the needs at the regulatory level in the manufacturing sector, which can serve as a model for other domains in the future.
2. Map developing activities carried out by ESOs, SDOs, Fora and consortia, LSPs, PPPs, DE/IT/FR trilateral cooperation, other research projects, etc., relevant to the digitalization of European industry.
3. Develop a model for synchronizing the various standardization activities, at Member State level, at European level and in a global context.

4. Propose a first roadmap that takes into account existing work, such as national standardization roadmaps and other related work, and specify concrete actions that can be included in the Rolling Plan for ICT Standardization.

3. Problem and proposed approach

3.1 Steel AM process chain optimization of finishing operations

Additive manufacturing processes are particularly attractive for material-efficient production of items that would otherwise have a high “buy-to-fly ratio”. The buy-to-fly (BTF) ratio is simply the ratio of the mass of the starting billet of material to the mass of the final, finished part. BTF ratios of 10-to-1 are common in aerospace applications – meaning that only 10 percent of the original material that is acquired remains in the final part – when parts are produced by traditional subtractive manufacturing processes. High BTF ratios are encountered when the geometry of the final part requires a large billet of material, sized by the extreme dimensions of the part, but most of this volume is removed and discarded using conventional subtractive manufacturing. The BTF plays a decisive role in the comparison of manufacturing technologies and approaches. Overall, AM approach emits less carbon dioxide (Figure 11) and emissions can be reduced by more than 50%. The main emission reduction is not dependent on the transport distance or the transport method. The BTF ratio is the key driver when it comes to emission reduction. The lower the BTF ratio, the lower is the energy input for production and transport emission of the raw material (Rupp, 2022).

Figure 11. Emission for the buy-to-fly ratio scenario [kg CO₂], from (Rupp, 2022).

Despite their numerous advantages, AM methods have some drawbacks, such as poor surface quality as a primary concern. Parts with poor surface qualities are not practicable in situations where high fatigue strength or glossy surfaces are preferred. Therefore, AMed parts should be subjected to additional surface finish operations to improve surface quality and eliminate the negative effects of surface roughness, pores, cracks, anisotropy, residual stresses, thermal stresses and laser spattering. *SuPreAM* will study different post-processing techniques, including milling, turning, electrical discharge machining and polishing to improve surface integrity. These processes have proved their capability to **improve the mechanical properties** and reduce the residual stresses formation and surface finish of AM products **up to 50 %** (Zhao, 2021).

Figure 12. Tensile properties of as-built, shallow-machined, deep-machined parts and standard ASTM F3055 for AMed (electron beam melting) Inconel 718 (Zhao, 2021).

The use of AM is on the rise in every sector because of the versatility of creating bespoke designs, one-off prototypes, or complex components that cannot be machined. However, without the correct finish, these components may fail at the early assessment stage in an industry that tests and re-tests to the breaking point. When the machinability of an alloy is known, the machining processes can be executed more efficiently: the right tool geometry and tool material can be selected, the cutting data can be adjusted for improved productivity, and scrap rates can be reduced.

Table 4. Identified challenges and proposed SuPreAM approach for steel AM process chain optimization of finishing operations.

Challenge	SuPreAM approach
1) Limitation on steel powders available for AM	Develop steel powders for AM applications
2) Poor resolution of the parts due to deposition of thick layers in DED technology	Use of MELTIO technology, a disruptive DED printing technology to produce denser parts
3) Scarce information about cutting tools damaging mechanisms during AMed machining and their effect on final surface integrity	Analyse the behaviour of different cutting tool materials to establish a relationship between surface integrity obtained from different cutting tools and component functionality
4) Scarce knowledge on thermochemical processes (e.g. nitriding) and hard coating application on AMed materials	Boost surface treatment of additive parts to help reduce costs
5) Current study on residual stress in AM is in the nascent stage	Nanoindentation technique will be used, in addition to conventional techniques, to evaluate residual stresses

3.2 Predictive simulation models on surface integrity towards zero defect manufacturing

Many individual technical factors affect production efficiency. For machining processes, it is not at all unusual for one or more of 50 - 70 individual factors to have an appreciable effect on efficiency. Typical factors include tools/tooling systems, workpiece configuration and materials, equipment process capabilities and data, human factors, peripheral equipment and maintenance issues. According to machining companies in SuPreAM consortium, between 5-10 % of machined components may require re-processing due to lack of surface quality when talking about conventional manufactured steels. However, due to the complexity of AMed steels this percentage could be higher depending on the type of piece and application. This entails high costs in repair work and/or elimination of defective pieces as scrap, in addition to production stoppages and replacement of machining tools in order to obtain pieces with the desired quality. For components of high added value and shorter series, the operation times are usually high in order to avoid the generation of defective parts, so that productivity is negatively affected. SuPreAM aims to increase the efficiency and competitiveness of the processes by producing components with optimal surface roughness and integrity. Four distinctive strategies based on overarching themes for zero defect manufacturing (ZDM) can be identified and highlighted: detection, repair, prediction, and prevention. Considering ongoing ZDM research and development it is expected prediction and prevention to grow significantly, due to the fact that these strategies when implemented effectively can avoid production of a defected part before the occurrence, rather than repairing it once a defect has already occurred.

Table 5. Identified challenges and proposed SuPreAM approach for predictive simulation models on surface integrity towards zero defect manufacturing.

Challenge	SuPreAM approach
6) Simulation of machining processes where the workpiece material is highly deformed during metal cutting is a major challenge of the finite element method (FEM)	Apply Particle Finite Element Method (PFEM) to prevent the typical difficulties of FEM
7) Current predictive systems lack the integration of the different systems affecting surface integrity	Integration of the influence of steels, the manufacturing technologies and machining strategies in the development of the predictive models
8) Scarce knowledge related to modelling of machining of AMed materials	Develop a tool to quantify the surface quality (in terms of roughness and residual stresses) from cutting processes and EDM

3.3 Methodology

The methodology comprises 5 main phases; from 1st to 4th increase the starting level and reach the targeted impact indicators, and the 5th validate the proposed solutions.

The comprehensive methodology is outlined in the SuPreAM project's Document of Activities (DoA). A concise overview of this methodology is presented below, with a focus on

addressing the challenges highlighted in Table 4 and Table 5 throughout the course of project implementation.

3.3.1 Phase 1: Additive manufacturing of conventional and novel steels towards improving machining operations

This Phase will be executed through the study of the influence of AM process, steel microstructure, chemical composition, heat treatment and mechanical properties of AMed steel alloys.

3.3.1.1 Use cases

Two representative case studies will be studied throughout the project. In both cases, the selected components are real in-use parts proposed for improvement with requirements closely related to surface quality:

1) **AMed injection mould**. It has conformal cooling channels and complex geometries all together with extreme requirements of surface roughness on those areas that will be in contact with the molten plastic to obtain high quality parts. Surface integrity is crucial to ensure quality of moulded parts and mould behaviour, thermal fatigue and wear resistance. Therefore, the surface roughness due to the AM must be completely removed by means of milling, EDM and finishing processes.

2) **AMed structural component for aerospace application** with a complex geometry. The printed workpiece will be machined to achieve the final dimensions and fatigue resistance. Milling and turning will be these machining processes.

In both case studies benchmarking with conventional manufactured and machined steels will be conducted.

3.3.1.2 Materials

•[1st Application] AMed injection mould.

The most used steel grades in AM of moulds are: 1.2709 (M300 maraging steel) and Stainless Steel CX. Both materials have been preliminary selected from the very restricted list of commercially available steel grades for Laser Based-Powder bed fusion (LB-PBF) technology. Moreover, in the framework of *SuPreAM* project AMIII will optimize AM of one of their internally developed steel powders for LB-PBF (WO Patent No. 123895 A1, 2021), (WO Patent No. 124069 A1, 2021), (WO Patent No. 124229 A1, 2021). The proposed material belongs to the lean maraging steels family (WO Patent No. 123894 A1, 2021). Lean maraging steels were developed to show a pseudo-stainless steels corrosion behaviour when they contain more than 8wt% Cr. Its resistance to corrosion is close to that shown by maraging stainless alloys and much higher than that shown by High Ni maraging reference steel. Concerning new potential business cases, maraging alloys showing pseudo-stainless steels corrosion behaviour could be used for mild corrosion environments and applications, such as food industry, paste & paper and oil & gas. Thus, the chemical compositions are tailored to reach high strength levels with a low alloying cost as compared to the reference M300 commercial maraging steel, containing high Co and high Ni. The composition design is based on alloying with 5 to 8 wt.% Cr for corrosion resistance and about 7wt.% of Ni with

addition of Al, Ti and/or Si to ensure the intermetallic precipitation and then the strengthening of the alloys. Throughout this case study, the commercial 1.2709 (M300 maraging steel) and AMIII's developed lean maraging steel (Lean-Si MS) will be compared and their performance evaluated for the specific mould application.

- [2nd Application] AMed structural component for aerospace application.

The conventionally manufactured part is machined from a precipitation hardening class of stainless steel DIN 1.4534 (X3CrNiMoAl13-8-2). Characteristically, the 1.4534 precipitation hardening stainless steel exhibits properties such as high hardness, excellent strength and superior toughness, in addition to good corrosion resistance properties. Typically, the applications of the alloy include the manufacture of components in the field of aerospace, petrochemical and nuclear industries. For this application, the most optimal material among the ones available for both AM technologies that are proposed, LB-PBF using powder format and DED using wire as feed material, will be selected. Potential candidates should have high strength, good corrosion resistance, and good mechanical properties. Among others, martensitic precipitation hardening stainless steels are a family of materials that are strong candidates for this application.

Challenge 1: There is a limitation on the number of steel powders available for AM. One of the main reasons that additive manufacturing technology is not fully implemented industrially in many potential applications is the limited availability of new materials. Additionally, these are costly materials with much higher price tags than the materials used in traditional manufacturing. *SuPreAM* builds upon our previous experience synthesizing special steel alloys for AM, adjusting manufacturing and printing parameters, and characterizing AMed components. Specifically, we plan to additionally improve machinability of AMed components from steel powders developed for AM applications.

3.3.1.3 Additive Manufacturing process

Three main technological approaches (based on Additive Manufacturing) have been identified and will be implemented into the selected use-cases. Those are: (i) LB-PBF (Laser Based-Powder bed fusion) [Powder], (ii) DED (Direct Energy Deposition) [Wire], (iii) Hybrid (Conventional machining + DED). More detailed information about these processes can be found in Section 2.1.

Challenge 2: A main drawback of DED technology is the poor resolution of the parts produced due to deposition of thick layers, increasing porosity and the need of post-process machining. In *SuPreAM*, a disruptive DED printing technology will be explored. Going under the commercial name of "MELTIO", this process uses a patented novel multi-laser system as source of energy for consolidation of raw material, which can be equally powder or wire in the same machine, even simultaneously (United States Patent No. 10661343B2, 2020). This technology produces 100% fully dense parts, which allows meeting the requirements of most critical applications. Besides, a wide range of materials is supported (Inconel, titanium, different grades of steel, among others). The technology is faster and cheaper than current alternatives, so it is expected to be a valuable alternative for industrial 3D printing of metals in the short term.

Figure 13. Examples of steel parts printed with a 'MELTIO' machine using wire DED technology.

3.3.1.4 Design of heat treatments

It is well known that most of the materials manufactured with AM technologies need heat treatment (HT) after printing so that the desired microstructure and, as consequence, the goal properties are achieved, see Section 2.2.3. There is a big number of possible combinations between steel alloy compositions and different heat treatments. Besides this, the additive manufacturing process parameters have an impact on the final material properties that must be considered. SuPreAM experienced consortium will perform a systematic study within the project to obtain the best material, heat treatment and technology combination.

3.3.2 Phase 2: Development of machining strategies for Additive Manufactured steels towards optimal surface integrity

Post-processing machining of AMed components is required in order to achieve end-user final requirements. Strategies will be defined according to the two different topics: 1) machining processes; and 2) finishing processes, see Section 2.2.1 and 2.2.2.

Challenge 3: Scarce information about cutting tools damaging mechanisms during AMed machining and their effect on final surface integrity. *SuPreAM* will analyse the behaviour of different cutting tool materials, taking advantage of consortium knowledge in previous and current related projects. Specific tasks will be carried out to establish a relationship between surface integrity obtained from different cutting tools and component functionality.

Challenge 4: Scarce knowledge on thermochemical processes (e.g. nitriding) and hard coating application on AMed materials. Although it has been identified as a need, there are few scientific publications on these topics. AMed parts and tools can be produced directly in-house, reducing logistics and travel costs. In that sense the production of tools and components that now is done outside Europe, will come back and OEMs will need to seek into local post-processing companies because it makes no sense to use coaters in Asia if their tools and parts are being made in Europe. Hence, as the trend in domestic additive

manufacturing increases, SuPreAM is going to boost surface treatment of additive parts to help reduce costs and keep the entire supply chain within Europe.

3.3.3 Phase 3: Machining processes and component behaviour modelling

Models of machining processes of AMed steels will be developed in the framework of this 3rd Phase.

3.3.3.1 Cutting and EDM machining process modelling

In SuPreAM project milling and turning will be studied as representative cutting processes in the development of 2D and 3D models. Milling (Figure 14a) and turning (Figure 14b) can be studied in 2D and 3D. The bi-dimensional case will be considered to easily characterize the simulations and their calibration. The mathematical formulation for the solid material is the same in the bi-dimensional and three-dimensional cases. However, the treatment of the geometry and the contact mechanics increases considerably in 3D. The simplest method configuration will be used to characterize the material models, contact and tribology properties. Milling and turning share some modelling processes in 3D but must be treated separately. The particular shape of chips produced by a sharp rotatory tool tip in milling operations need for special geometrical considerations, mesh refinement and contact definitions.

Figure 14. a) Scheme of 2D and 3D models for milling, b) scheme of 3D model for turning.

In the case of Electrical Discharge Machining (EDM), modelling is required to increase the competitiveness of the process in the manufacturing industry (Maradia, 2015), due to the many control parameters involved. SuPreAM will develop an EDM model employing FEM solver and governing process laws of the process consisting of a multi-physics framework able to deal with both the electric and the thermal fields as well as the fluid-flow analysis able to predict the material removal by the electro-discharge process.

Challenge 6: The numerical simulation of metal cutting processes is extremely complex mainly due to two factors: i) the material characterization and ii) the boundary characterization. The first one needs constitutive models to represent both high and low strength rate deformation under a wide range of temperatures. The material behaviour must also consider hardening and softening processes involved in the plasticity phenomena (Wedberg, 2012), (Svoboda, 2010). The second complex factor is the severe geometry distortions produced by machining processes, combined with the presence of contacts and the generation of new surfaces. These are difficult to handle by current numerical modelling techniques available in commercial software when they are present all together. To

overcome these difficulties, in the framework of SuPreAM, the cutting process model will be developed using the Particle Finite Element Method (PFEM). This method has shown promising results in the modelling of materials subjected to large deformation of the workpieces, thanks to the physics provided by solid mechanics and fluid dynamics (Rodriguez J. e., 2016), (Rodriguez J. e., 2018), (Rodriguez J. e., 2019), (Carbonell, 2020). In the framework of AVINT project (AVINT, 2021), coordinated by EUT, and with the participation of CIMNE (both SuPreAM consortium members), PFEM predicted residual stress maps (Figure 15), cutting forces and roughness parameters, i.e., Ra at mean absolute errors of 0.03 μm in the control group prediction.

Figure 15. Residual stress distribution on a cross section of aluminium machined surface (7000 rpm, feed rate of 0.02 mm/rev and worn tool equivalent to 1000 machined pieces) from AVINT project.

It is worth mentioning that there are no references related to modelling of machining of AMed materials. SuPreAM tasks include review of methods and available techniques, mathematical study of models, development of equations, calibration of models via benchmarking or experimental data, and implementation via programming code in a multi-physics platform for its integration in large numerical simulations. In this manner the previous knowledge will be levelled up and adapted to the specific features of AMed steels. In order to develop correct material models and accurately reproduce the material behaviour, tasks to evaluate materials and surface parameters will be carried out, as well as the calibration of the developed laws for contact and friction to reproduce chip formation. The resultant surface integrity of the AMed machined workpieces depends on chip generation when cutting the material.

Challenge 7: Machine learning (ML) algorithms, such as neural networks, fuzzy logic, evolutionary algorithms, etc., are also applied to machining processes, using empirical data to define model parameters (Oñate, 2014), (Preez, 2019), (Kim, 2018), (Tseng, 2016). ML algorithms are very powerful predictive tools, however, due to their complexity, these models cannot provide analytical relationships between the input and output data and are often referred to as “black boxes” as the user loses insight into the underlying physics. The main challenge in using ML approaches is that the approximation error converges to reasonable values only with a large amount of data, which is often difficult and expensive to obtain in

machining operations. The use of ML approaches in conjunction with FEM approaches has recently seen a lot of interest, since FEM is the tool of choice for understanding the effect and is capable to provide numerical data, to overcome the limitation of data volume in ML. SuPreAM aim is to analyse the relationship between the different machining process parameters (speed, feed rate) and materials (AMed steels, cutting tools) to the resulting surface integrity, see Figure 16. Furthermore, numerical models developed in SuPreAM will be able to connect to ML to further provide hybrid solutions.

Figure 16. Information flow summary: model inputs and outputs relationship and interaction between partners for predictive model set-up within WP4.

3.3.3.2 Component behaviour modelling

For 1st application, the filling stage of thermoplastic injection moulding will be numerically studied with a solver based on PFEM to verify the functionality of the suggested mould design and to study the influence of process variables to optimize processing conditions. The numerical model is used to predict the melt flow front interface and fields (pressure, velocity, and temperature). For the 2nd application, the component will be numerically modelled with the finite element method (FEM) and simulated under suitable loading conditions to predict eventual large stress concentrations.

3.3.4 **Phase 4: Surface integrity characterisation of AMed steels after post-processing**

In this phase the most important machined component features will be described in terms of surface integrity. In addition, the machinability of the AM materials will be evaluated considering the steel quality, the AM process, heat treatment, cutting tool and/or post-processing parameters. In general terms, surface integrity is commonly defined as “the topographical, mechanical, chemical and metallurgical state of a machined surface and its relationship to functional performance”. The different topics and categories to describe surface integrity are detailed in Section 2.3.

Challenge 5: Current study on residual stress in AM is in the nascent stage, future research directions remain to be explored include measurement methods for macro/micro residual

stresses, crystal structure, simulation, in-process and post-process mitigation, and the impacts on part dimensional accuracy and functionality such as fracture and fatigue resistance, creep, and corrosion. Residual stress measurement resolution by means of XRD and hole drilling is 0.5 and 1 mm, respectively. In *SuPreAM*, additionally to type I residual stresses measurements, type II residual stresses will be evaluated by means of Nanoindentation technique. This method for estimating residual stresses imposed by instrumented sharp indentation was developed by Suresh et al. (Suresh, 1998). The authors noticed that the indentation behaviour is affected by the presence of residual stresses. For a fixed penetration depth with tensile residual stresses there is an increase in the indentation load, whereas a decrease in indentation load takes place when compressive residual stresses are present. Thus, using nanoindentation technique the residual stresses and their sign in the subsurface of machined samples could be determined (Wang Q. e., 2006), (Lara, 2018). In Figure 17 an example of load-depth curves obtained for the same tool steel with different surface finishes is shown. In this example compressive stresses are more severe depending on machining and finishing processes. Nanoindentation results will be compared with XRD and hole drilling in order to validate the methodologies implemented during *SuPreAM* project. Thickness of affected layers and residual stress profiles will be compared with modelling and simulation results, in order to compare predicted results from the model with experimental results and perform the necessary adjustments. Additive manufactured samples before and after heat treatment and conventional steel samples after machining and finishing will be also analysed using an in situ micro-tensile testing machine and the results will be correlated with local variations of E and residual stresses.

Figure 17. Load vs. depth curves of a tool steel with different surface finishes.

3.3.5 Phase 5: Validation of the proposed solutions considering additive manufacturing technologies, steel alloys, heat treatment, post-processing strategies and models

Throughout this phase it will be demonstrated, from one side, how two real components, quite different between them, are suitable for being produced by additive manufacturing technologies and suitable for its use in real demanding application after proper heat treatment

and machining, and from another side, how the models predict surface integrity of the demonstrators. The current additive manufacturing technologies have some printing limitations that will have to be considered for the final design (e.g., minimum and maximum thickness, size, resolution depending on printing direction, aspect ratio, materials, overhangs, etc). These design features are really dependent on the type of additive technology selected. Once the design guidelines will be established, and regarding the material and technology selected, a new design will be done. This redesign will be mainly based on topological optimization of the nominal design (the current design of the components), starting from this nominal design a finite element problem will be constructed taking into account the material properties and the loads present in each component. After solving the numerical problem, the main stress paths will be determined. Depending on the final application the new design will remove mass till the safety factor which its value will be justified.

[1st Application] AMed injection mould: DRT will manufacture the mould inserts by adopting the previously selected additive manufacturing techniques and materials. At least, two final demonstrators will be produced to keep one of them for the evaluation of in-service behaviour and the second for the necessary destructive test for characterization and quality assurance.

[2nd Application] AMed structural component for aerospace application: The combination of the technology design capabilities within the inputs of the requirements of the part will have the outcome of the final bionic design of the demonstrator [AMIII]. Several designs and iteration might be required before obtaining the desired and final model to build the demonstrators. With the new bionic design, the demonstrator should present a reduction in weight as well keep its mechanical performance within the limits of the application. In addition, the design needs to take the finishing operations into account (e.g., clamping of component on CNC-machines). Three complete demonstrators will be produced to perform the necessary tests.

Demonstrators of machining models will be carried out according to the final application requirements. The strategy will consider the new redesign of the components. Once the parts will be machined, surface integrity (residual stress and roughness) will be measured with the techniques tested, mapping in this way the most critical areas of the part. Once the experimental values will be registered, they will be compared against the prediction of the numerical model developed and calibrated. For comparison purposes, conventional steel machined demonstrators will be also produced.

Figure 18. Predictive models developed in the framework of SuPreAM for optimal surface integrity.

A sensitive analysis will be carried out by varying the parameters of the machining processes (milling, turning, EDM) through the execution of the numerical simulations.

Components behaviour models will be validated: 1st application, the injection process will be simulated to verify all functionalities and parameters. In addition, the demonstrator will be validated by producing several batches of plastic pieces. Inserts obtained by AMed and conventional steels will be tested. 2nd application, to validate the numerical simulation and to study the influence of surface integrity on the fatigue behaviour of the structural component, the demonstrator produced (minimum of 3 components) will be tested in a fatigue bench. Additionally, mechanical behaviour will be compared to conventional steel structural workpiece.

In the framework of SuPreAM project four models are developed, the sum of them consists of a powerful tool enabling the identification of main variables affecting surface integrity of studied industrial cases. The sensitivity analysis will be carried out and as a final conclusion of SuPreAM project, a complete list of the main parameters that affect the surface integrity of machined parts will be obtained.

4. Outcomes

SuPreAM purposes the investigation in a holistic approach of the main factors affecting part quality of additive manufactured + machined steel products:

The aim of SuPreAM is to optimize the surface integrity of Additive Manufactured and Machined steel components and to reduce manufacturing expenditures at the steel industrial sector through the minimization of the material scrap up to 35% (#EO1) and reducing the number of re-processing loops during finishing operations keeping defective parts below 2% (#EO2) of additive manufactured components.

The main objectives to be tackled to this purpose can be summarised as follows:

#OB1: To develop and improve the performance and capabilities of a predictive simulation model of finishing operations in steel Additive Manufacturing (AM).

#OB2: To optimize the surface integrity of steel additive manufactured (AMed) components. Achievement of these objectives will give rise to secondary objectives, related to increasing component quality and competitiveness and to optimizing process parameters through materials modification and process stability assurance:

#SO1: To develop an in-house software module for the simulation of milling/turning and finishing processes based on particle finite element method (PFEM).

#SO2: To develop an in-house software module for the simulation of the electrical discharge machining (EDM) process.

#SO3: To evaluate steel grades for surface integrity optimization of AMed and machined parts and to implement novel lean maraging steel in AM.

#SO4: To determine the influence of steel AM technology, machining strategies, machining process parameters and cutting tool materials on machinability and surface properties of AMed components.

#SO5: To identify and describe the most significant AMed and machined component characteristics concerning surface topography, microstructure, metallurgical and mechanical properties through advanced characterization techniques.

#SO6: To establish surface integrity and functionality relationship: identification of main parameters affecting surface integrity.

4.1 Expected Outcomes of SuPreAM project

#EO1: Minimization of the material scrap by boosting the implementation of additive manufacturing with optimal surface integrity

SuPreAM will provide a fundamental understanding of the surface integrity resulting from both additive manufacturing and post-processing, which is crucial to properly design the interlinked manufacturing routes and to improve the resultant performance and functionality of AM parts. In that manner it is expected that at least **12% increase on AMed + machined parts** could be manufactured by this new approach instead of conventional machining, according to the expertise of consortium members, for mould applications this increase can be up to 15%, and in aerospace components up to 8%, among all resulting in a **decrease of scrap of 35%** (90% reduction originating from new AMed components, see Section 3.1). *SuPreAM* will deliver the tools to properly design these parts that nowadays cannot be AMed

due to a lack of surface integrity and unawareness of resulting functionality after manufacturing and post-processing. This #EO1 is directly related to RFCS' Objective 8 (b) [Downstream] **steel process and process chain optimisation** (including casting, rolling, **finishing** and coating operations) via instrumentation, detection of properties of intermediate and final products, modelling, control and automation, including digitalisation, application of big data, artificial intelligence and any other advanced technologies).

Market scale: Additive Manufacturing market is believed to be the most widely used in 3D printing. With interesting mechanical characteristics for industries such as aerospace or automotive, it is not surprising to witness this increase. Additionally, 3D printing has been identified for the EU as disruptive technology, that will promote Europe to make the most of localisation as an opportunity to bring more manufacturing back to the EU in some sectors. The Europe AM market is expected to grow significantly in the forecast period of 2023 to 2030. Data Bridge Market Research analyses that the market is growing with a CAGR of 20.7% in the forecast period of 2023 to 2030 and is expected to reach USD 26,187.15 million by 2030 (Data Bridge Market Research, 2023), see Figure 19. The primary factor driving the growth of the additive manufacturing market is the increasing demand for lightweight components from the automotive and aerospace industries, ease of manufacturing complex design with short production cycle time, growing demand for AM from various industries, and positive outlook for AM in the construction industry. **Target groups:** All (see Table 6). **Linked objectives:** #OB1, #OB2, #SO1, #SO1, #SO2, #SO3, #SO4, #SO5, #SO6.

Europe Additive Manufacturing Market is Expected to Account for USD 26,187.15 Million by 2030

Figure 19. Evolution of Europe AM market from 2023 to 2030 (Data Bridge Market Research, 2023).

#EO2: Reducing the number of re-processing loops during finishing operations towards zero defect manufacturing

Many individual technical factors affect production efficiency. For machining processes, it is not at all unusual for one or more of 50 - 70 individual factors to have an appreciable effect on efficiency. Typical factors include tools/tooling systems, workpiece configuration and materials, equipment process capabilities and data, human factors, peripheral equipment and maintenance issues. According to machining companies in *SuPreAM* consortium, between 5-10 % of machined components may require re-processing due to lack of surface quality when talking about conventional manufactured steels. However, due to the complexity of AMed steels this percentage could be higher depending on the type of piece and application. This entails high costs in repair work and/or elimination of defective pieces as scrap, in addition to production stoppages and replacement of machining tools in order to obtain pieces with the desired quality. For components of high added value and shorter series, the operation times are usually high in order to avoid the generation of defective parts, so that productivity is negatively affected. *SuPreAM* aims to increase the efficiency and competitiveness of the processes by producing components with optimal surface roughness and integrity. Four distinctive strategies based on overarching themes for zero defect manufacturing (ZDM) can be identified and highlighted: detection, repair, prediction, and prevention. Considering ongoing ZDM research and development it is expected prediction and prevention to grow significantly, due to the fact that these strategies when implemented effectively can avoid production of a defected part before the occurrence, rather than repairing it once a defect has already occurred. This #EO2 is directly related to RFCS' Objective 9 (d): **predictive simulation models on microstructures, mechanical properties and production processes.**

Value proposition: Through a careful adjustment of machining parameters taking into account AMed steels main features and defects high-quality surfaces can be achieved. Even though various metals can already be used in AM, finishing operations are yet a fresh area requiring intensive studies in terms of metal usage and parameter optimization. *SuPreAM* findings will provide the necessary knowledge to design and implement machining strategies that enable to **maintain defective AMed and machined components** due to surface defects **below 2%**.

Market scale: The metal machining market share is expected to increase by USD 12.63 billion from 2020 to 2025, and the market's growth momentum will accelerate at a CAGR of 3.11% as per the latest market report by Technavio. 38% of the market's growth will originate from Asia-Pacific region during the forecast period (Technavio, 2023). After China, the EU is the second biggest steel producer, with an average 170 million tonnes of crude steel produced per year and is the world leader in the highly technologically specialised product segment. The competitiveness of steel parts is enhanced by secondary operations which improve mechanical, functional and geometrical properties and machining is the most common manufacturing processes for producing parts and obtaining specified geometrical dimensions and surface finish. Currently machining processes represents around 15% of the value of all manufactured products in all industrialized countries. Metal cutting processes are present in large industries like automotive, aerospace, home appliance, etc., but also in high tech industries where small components with high precision are needed (European Commission, 2023). **Target groups:** All. **Linked objectives:** #OB1, #OB2, #SO1, #SO2, #SO3, #SO4, #SO5, #SO6.

Table 6. Target groups of SuPreAM.

Target group	Specific needs	SuPreAM solution	Value proposition
(TG1) Machining companies	Defining machining strategies to optimal surface integrity of additive manufactured + machined workpieces/parts/tools.	Strategies to select machining processes parameters and cutting tools materials to obtain proper process parameters to get high quality surface integrity of additive manufactured + machined steels.	SuPreAM will provide novel software for the numerical modelling of machining processes towards optimal surface integrity.
(TG2) Steelmakers	Design of steel alloys for AM respecting the GD strategies aiming at reducing, manufacturing expenses, waste and CO2 impact.	Evaluation of the benefits from a surface integrity point of view of AMed steel alloys, including novel lean maraging steel.	Knowledge to design steel alloys (chemical composition, heat treatment, thermo-mechanical properties) for AM with improved machinability.
(TG3) OEMs & part designers	Safer and cheaper components, and with low environmental impact and cost	Software to obtain components functionality depending on AMed material and machining strategy and cost-effective manufacturing processes, with reduced number of parts.	New conceptual methodologies to design components and parts subjected to mechanical requirements enabling competitiveness increase due to time and waste reduction during their manufacturing process.
(TG4) Tool /Mould manufacturers	Efficient tools/moulds with high surface quality	Software to obtain tools/moulds functionality depending on AMed material and machining strategy.	New conceptual methodologies to improve design of tools and moulds subjected to surface requirements enabling competitiveness increase due to life duration prolongation and waste reduction during their manufacturing.
(TG5) Equipment manufacturers	Additive manufacturing and machining equipment with digital tools to	Novel software for the numerical modelling of machining processes towards optimal surface integrity that can be	Cost-effective technologies to reduce defects and reworking during machining by means

Target group	Specific needs	SuPreAM solution	Value proposition
	improve product quality towards zero-waste, driving the growth of EU industry linked to new manufacturing technologies.	integrated in machining equipment. Additionally, knowledge on AM process parameters to provide best machinability of resulting parts.	of better surface integrity of finished parts towards zero-defect and zero-waste.
(TG6) Innovation and R&D managers	Respect the GD guidelines integrating and testing new materials, and digital solutions.	Multidisciplinary international Consortium capable of creating a unique solution to tackle the topic challenges.	New insight and knowledge to be shared in open access following FAIR criteria.
(TG7) Testing laboratories and researchers	Identify the material properties that better describe the surface integrity of AMed + machined materials and develop innovative and efficient lab tests.	Gain knowledge on AMed + machined materials properties and behaviour.	Testing solutions to estimate surface integrity of AMed + machined materials aimed at optimizing materials design for AM applications.
(TG8) Public Authorities for Social and Occupational affairs, Employees	Making Europe the first digitally enabled circular climate-neutral and sustainable economy.	Foster the strength of EU Industry on research and innovation and promoting big players, SME and RTO collaboration	New cost-effective solutions to strengthen the EU industries and contribute to reinforce the uptake of new technologies provided by SMEs and Large companies
(TG9) Citizens	Safer and cheaper products, and with low environmental impact	Optimization of quality and functionality relationship of new components obtained by AM, or with AMed moulds	New products with higher quality and lower cost.

4.2 SuPreAM contribution to the wider impacts (IMP)

#IMP1: Impact on European Sustainable Industry Policy

SuPreAM proposal is aligned with the European Green Deal (GD) Sustainable Industry Policy Area focussed on energy-intensive industries, such as steel, which according to the GD “are indispensable to Europe’s economy, as they supply several key value chains. The decarbonisation and modernisation of this sector is essential.” Producing high quality near-net shape components: advanced and efficient manufacturing processes that enable decreasing the use of energy, raw materials and other natural resources, increasing the use of secondary raw materials, closing the industrial water, energy and materials’ loops and reducing GHG emissions and pollution are significant advances to reinforce EU industry and economy and give a response to address systemic crisis such as climate change and the

recovery from the COVID-19 pandemic. The use of AM contributes significantly at reducing production time and costs in the industrial supply chain, especially in sectors such Tooling Industry, where moulds and tooling with high surface quality and complex geometries are required, as well as in Aerospace and Automotive sectors which entail structural workpieces with high mechanical resistance and complex geometries also. AM can reduce the “cradle-to-gate” environmental footprints of component manufacturing through avoidance of tools, dies, and materials scrap associated with conventional manufacturing processes. The project will contribute to the GD by reducing the scrap, since quality of the components/moulds will be predicted before finishing processes necessary to obtain optimal surface integrity, machining parameters will be adjusted to obtain surfaces with zero defects, coupled with savings in raw materials achieved with AM itself. Additionally, *SuPreAM* is aligned with challenges established in Cluster 4 of Horizon Europe, more specifically with destination “Climate neutral, circular and digitised production” and with the key strategic objective of Making Europe the first digitally led circular, climate-neutral and sustainable economy through the transformation of its mobility, energy, construction and production systems.’ and fits within the strategic research and innovation agenda of “Made in Europe”, the manufacturing partnership with the European Commission under the Framework Programme 'Horizon Europe' (2021_2027). Additionally, Clean Steel Partnership is co-programmed in Horizon Europe, through Cluster 4 and Cluster 5, and *SuPreAM* is aligned with its focus group about “Low Carbon and Energy Efficiency” where new technologies within the whole value chain are needed for the reduction of the CO₂ emissions to achieve the political goals of climate neutrality in 2050.

#IMP2: Impact on European industry

In an industrial scenario where the demand for productivity and high quality of manufactured parts go hand in hand, it becomes crucial to equip machines with forefront diagnostic and control systems that increase efficiency and durability reducing scrap at the same time. There have been rapid developments in intelligent machining. Increasing automatization of manufacturing processes and other sectors has created an unprecedented demand for intelligent machining. In line with it, the model developed in *SuPreAM* will provide machine tools with a robust and unique tool to predict part quality prior to its production and to successfully develop this holistic model, a multidisciplinary European consortium has been created integrating all the actors of metal removal process. The machine tool industry is fundamental for the productivity and competitiveness of the entire European manufacturing base. Machine Tools market worldwide is projected to grow by EUR 33.8 billion, driven by a compounded growth of 6.2 per cent (study period 2015-2024). Machining sector is one of the rare industries expected to witness a robust growth due to COVID19. Even if most of the forecasts come true, machining industry is expected to give a significant push to the sagging global economy. Representing the developed world, the United States will maintain a 5.3 % growth. Within Europe, Germany will add over EUR 1.2 billion to the region’s size and clout in the next five to six years. Over EUR 1 billion worth of projected demand in the region will come from Rest of Europe markets (Machine tools World, 2023).

#IMP3: Impact on European economy

Using AM, the waste is practically eliminated, since the necessary material is supplied to produce almost exclusively the required shape, and parts with defects can be completely recycled. This contributes to building the circular economy and favours the sustainability of manufacturing resources. The material used can be optimized through design modifications, allowing for even stronger and lighter parts. Parts assemblies can be produced in one

operation, reducing the number of final assembly operations and increasing the reliability of the resulting product. The possibility of producing locally at a reduced cost means a radical transformation of the current supply chain: the transport routes can be greatly reduced. Additionally, with *SuPreAM*, there is a significant delay reduction in the AM process because it detects errors in part quality, increasing the efficiency of an improved lean supply chain and increasing the turnover. Organizations will be able to meet the market with better efficiency, higher quality, lower cost, and lower delivery time, increasing the market share with a contribution to economic development and profitability. In sum, project findings will strengthen EU innovative capacity in the steel sector and increase the competitiveness of machining companies to build up their position towards competitors.

#IMP4: Impact on European society

Thanks to the *SuPreAM* optimisation of the technology, it will rise the attractiveness of working in the field of AM, which will provide an improvement in the employee work satisfaction and percentages of high skilled workers. Therefore, it will also increase and afford AM training, the presence of AM in higher education through knowledge sharing, a higher percentage of the workforce hired locally and the organization's efforts in promoting AM education initiatives in the local community through corporate social responsibility. It has also been demonstrated that AM technologies foster job creation via multiplier effects in several industries (software development, CAD systems, product-design, optimisation analysis, etc) but most significantly throughout the pre-production (how one can design a model to be manufactured with AM systems regardless of limitation of traditional manufacturing technologies) and post-production (referring to quality control and repeatability of a fabricated part) stages of a part with AM. *SuPreAM* will maintain and create 9.9 full-time employees (FTE) within the consortium for the period 2023-2026. Beyond the impact in employment, such type of initiatives also increases awareness of the environmental impacts at societal level. Solutions that also address the EU dependency on imports of Critical Raw Materials (CRMs) and other valuable resources, have been considered by the EU to have economic, social and environmental benefits and that should be promoted. *SuPreAM* will improve the awareness of relevant external stakeholders and the general public across the EU about the importance of raw materials for society, the challenges related to their supply within the EU and about proposed solutions which could help to improve society's acceptance of and trust in sustainable raw materials production.

#IMP5: Impact on environment

As the European Green Deal argues, the EU's industry has started a shift towards climate neutral and circular economy, but still accounts for 20% of the EU's greenhouse gas emissions. It remains too 'linear', and dependent on a throughput of new materials extracted, traded and processed into goods, and finally disposed of as waste or emissions. The transition is an opportunity to expand sustainable and job-intensive economic activity. There is significant potential in global markets for low-emission technologies, sustainable products and services. Likewise, the circular economy offers great potential for new activities and jobs. In this regard, *SuPreAM* will reduce material wastage and minimise the need for post processing through subtractive methods by using AM as a key driver for the machining sector. There are two key elements that give AM the quality of an environmentally friendly technology and consider it a sustainable manufacturing method. First, it reduces waste, since unlike subtractive manufacturing, AM employs only the necessary material when adding layer by layer. The second point is the improved accessibility of AM technologies, enhanced by Industry 4.0, provided to manufacturers, since they can now produce directly in-house,

reducing logistics and travel costs. Regarding life cycle of the product, AM can be fairly advantageous. When a product comprised of several pieces is fabricated, AM allows the manufacturer to produce isolated parts. Also allows the addition of new parts or the replacement of better ones, which optimizes and extends the life cycle of the original product. The possibility of creating lighter parts affects the use of the object, for example, fuel consumption and the emissions caused by it. Furthermore, the prospect of the possible recycling and use/reuse tools for extended life, since some researchers explore the recycling of metal powder (Godina, 2020). Additionally, up taking *SuPreAM*, companies can obtain benefits as environmentally responsible enterprise delivering green products with the consequent increase of customer satisfaction.

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